

Coleoptera_Myxophaga

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Cyathoceridae: *Lepidocerus horni*

Myxophaga Hydroscaphidae: *Hydroscapha natans*

Microsporididae: *Microsporus ovenensis*

Torridincolidae: *Claudiella nigeus*

Like *Ytu* and *Hintonia*, this specimen shows clearly that MA and MP approach in parallel the posterior wing margin

Torridincolidae: *Hintonia britskii*

Hintonia shows position of MA, MP, and fusion of CuA branch to MP branch, plesiomorphic to all Coleoptera

Torridincolidae: n.g. ♂
Venezuela

Torridincolidae: *Ytu zeus*

Ytu shows clearly the branching of RA and RP

TORRIDINCOLIDAE : YTU ZEUS

close to Haliplidar

1.7 mm